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This report tends to review the literature tackling religious authority and knowledge tradition in Islam. Given the broad and multidimensional nature of the topic, this report zooms into religious authority and leadership by looking at various religious leaders, figures and actors involved in the process of transmitting Islamic knowledge.

These include all kind of religious leaders regardless of their status, position or role within the religious organizational landscape. They can be Ulama, prestigious scholars, jurists, Imams, preachers, prayers leaders, etc.

Introduction

The Traditional Transmission of Knowledge and Relations with Authority in Islam

In this report, we take the transmission of Islamic knowledge to be embedded within – though not exclusive to – such authority figures, as they are central to the production and dissemination of religious knowledge. They turn religious text into religious discourse. We look at three major schools of thought in Islam: the majority Sunni school, the Shia tradition that is the second-largest after Sunnism, and early Sufi thought that transcends sectarian divide.

This report aims to demonstrate the similarities and points of departure within these modes of understanding and practicing Islam and how the academic world's contemporary work on them. And it brings us closer to the blank spots in this body of literature. The co-writers have chosen to write on one tradition each, and narrow the literature reviewed specific to their individual research projects.

This serves to situate their research and is pragmatically necessitated, as confines of discipline and space make it impossible to provide a complete review of contemporary literature on Islam, although we realize that this divide may not always play a decisive role in actual situations and cases.

Part 1.

Religious Authority and Knowledge Transmission in the Shiite Tradition

By Aleeha Zahra (ESR 11)

In academic research on Islam, Shiism has occupied the same minority space as it does in most spaces outside of Iran. Recent work is burgeoning particularly on Shias in the West in response to migration, integration, conversion and the ways Shias and other Muslim communities organize themselves. This report's focus is on Twelver Shiism, and the work that has been done on authority within it. Authority in Twelver Shia Islam can be conceptualized as a wheel. The hub is the concept of the Imamate, where authority lies and is derived from. The spokes comprise of: the maraji' al-taqlid¹, the hawza (seminaries); ayatollahs, mujtahids (jurists), preachers, and local leaders; and lived practices such as rituals, prayers and worship.

In Iranian and Iraqi contexts studies have traced how figures such as Ayatollah Sistani and Muqtada al-Sadr blur the lines between quietist religious leader and powerful political actor, creating social, religious, and political implications. Directions in the transmission of authority have also been looked at, from linear hierarchies in a hawza,

to successions of maraji², to competing and collaborating networks of scholars spreading across different countries, regions and virtual environments. These authorities are dynamic and changing, with Kassem suggesting that hawzas react and adapt to new forms of knowledge. Rizvi looks at how a marja's authority is constructed in the digital age, with its reach expanding and becoming accessible to geographically-distant Shia communities. A marja's position is dependent on the people who follow them. Fibinger's study follows an Iraqi man in Kuwait searching for a marja and criticizes the lack of studies on authority from a "bottom-up" perspective.

Processes of mediation and their link to Shia authority, especially through the internet, have also garnered academic attention. The most popular maraji, such as Sistani and Khomeini, have their own websites with fatwas available in multiple languages and e-mail options for people to contact them. This changed access influences how people select a marja to emulate. Bunt looked at popular Shia websites, observing how they facilitate

exchanges between Shia scholars and practitioners whilst also filling leadership vacuums in some local communities. Eiselohr's study of Shias in Mumbai concludes that global processes, access to audiovisual media technologies, and national contexts combine to shape religious communication. Kalinock describes Iranian clerics using the internet for religious communication and dissemination, and believers using forums and online information to "bypass religious authority" and connect with "co-believers". The internet can also validate the authority of lay local organizations through affiliating them with established maraji.

Shiism has been studied in diaspora and minority contexts, particularly in Europe, with an emphasis on Iranian communities. In diaspora, Shiism is posited to take new forms, particularly transnational ones. According to Corboz, Rizvi and Scharbrodt authority in Shiism has traditionally maintained trans-local and transnational dimensions. The legacy of this can be observed in "new" migrant communities and their entangled relationship with authority. In

such spaces, Shia practices from different sources and countries can come into conflict over how to practice and which marja to follow. There is a disconnect amongst the rulings of maraji from the Middle East and the lived reality of Muslims in the West. In some ways, diaspora communities are better positioned to challenge traditional authority and introduce alternative forms. Studies attribute this to a greater agency that comes from people moving from established local contexts to new ones and gaining access to multiple traditions. Schlatmann's ethnography of Dutch Shia youth and Spellman-Poots' work in the UK describe young Shias organizing themselves in transnational groups, using their native languages (English and Dutch) for religious communication.

Broadly, it is attributed to Shia authority that it is constantly adapting to contemporary circumstances, encouraged by the transnational nature of its institutions such as the maraji' al-taqlid and hawza. This allows it to reshape and retain its relevance amidst shifting contexts.

Part 2.

Religious Authority and Knowledge Transmission in the Sunni Tradition

By Hayat Douhan (ESR 10)

There has been an increasing interest in religious authority in the last two decades. Given the broad and multidimensional aspects of the construct, researchers varied in how they researched it; while some approached it from a conceptual perspective, others have followed an “actor-centered approach” by focusing on religious leadership (Peter, 2006). To limit the scope of this review, I will follow the latter by focusing on imams as one of the key agents in the construction of religious authority and the traditional transmission of Islamic knowledge mainly among the diaspora in Europe. Since the notion of “imam” sometimes varies across Islamic traditions, for the purpose of this review I will use “imam” as known in the Sunni tradition, meaning the person who leads the daily prayers, delivers the Friday Sermons and provides Islamic ‘traditional’ teachings.

A body of researchers highlighted the complexity of considering the construct of religious authority within diasporic Muslim communities in the West (Mandaville, 2001; Saint-Blancat, 2002; Yukleyen, 2012; Serikov, 2014, Sunier & Landman, 2014). Mandaville (2001) shed light on the development of religious discourse among the diaspora stressing the potential role of information and communication technologies in reshaping the religious public sphere in this context. Serikov (2014) argued that what is called “Umma Islamiyya” is just an imaginary construct that was created by academic research and religious ideology obscuring the variety within the diaspora, which led several religious associations to claim the representative role over these communities. Similarly, Yukleyen (2012) highlighted the diversity among Turkish Islamic organizations, which reflects the fragmentation of religious authority among the Turkish religious field in the Europe. Another significant contribution to religious authority among the Turkish diaspora is Sunier and Landman’s (2015) extensive study of the Turkish religious field in

which they argue for the need to consider the various transnational social, cultural and religious aspects in the study of Islam in Europe. They not only traced the emergence and development of the Turkish religious landscape throughout three decades, but also debated some future trends.

Researchers vary in how they investigated religious authority at various levels. For instance, some studies researched it from a broader level by looking into the construct of religious authority across Europe. Unterreiner & Weinar (2014) found out that while various diasporic situations diverge in the impact of religion on the level of integration, they tend to converge in the clash between the religious leaders’ backgrounds and the community expectations. This has led to questioning the role of imams, their training and their transnational religious influence. Having explored the imam training across Europe, Husson (2007) found out that theological and integrative trainings are two key needs in all European countries. However, these vary tremendously in how they tackle this issue based mainly on the system of

Church-State relation. In this regard, El Asri (2018) argued for a local religious training that takes into account the specificities of the host country. Vinding (2018) provided a useful classification of imams that not only captures the variation among Islamic authorities in the West, but also consider their institutional expectations as well as their accompanying challenges. According to Nalborczyk’s (2019) study on the Tatar’s community in Poland, Vinding’s typology is still applicable among imams working with European indigenous Muslim communities.

Other researchers were more interested in gaining deeper insights about the construct by zooming on specific aspects or conditions. Many studies have focused on the relationship between religious and political authorities. Lotfi (2006) focused on the Moroccan religious field, highlighting the state’s increasing interest in managing religious affairs in a way to promote the “Moroccan Islam” model. Hashas (2018) argued that the imamate has become a context-based construct that is shaped by religious scholarship

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and political authorities. Having contrasted two models, he found out that the Moroccan imamate has been institutionalized by the state to serve its political agenda; whereas the French model mirrors the changing status and role of imams in a secular setting. Similarly, Jouanneau (2018) traced the development of the French “imamate”, stressing how it became a crucial issue in the public policies of a laic state revealing this latter’s efforts to collaborate with other Muslim entities to keep the French imamate under control. In a different context, Birt (2006) examined how the imamate has been constructed in relation to the government’s official discourse. This latter has initially stressed the state’s notion of “civic” religion framing the “good” imams as having integrative role in this process. However, such discourse changed after 9/11, conceptualizing “good” imams as agents of civil society who are expected to cooperate with the government to fight extremism promoted by their “bad” counterparts.

Having traced the discussion of religious training in Europe, some researchers zoomed into particular programs in an attempt to solve the puzzle of importing imams versus domestic training. Ghaly (2007) offered an analysis of three initiatives launched by the Dutch government stressing the major obstacles faced to apply a domestic Dutch imam training; while some are related to the Dutch secular context, others concern the imams or Muslim communities. Sozerm, Altinyelken & Volman (2019) attributed the failure these state-funded theological programs to the lack of trust of Muslim entities in these initiatives, the lack of confidence in the non-Muslim academics and the lack of cooperation from the leading Islamic organizations. While domestic imam training is proven to be challenging, some countries are increasingly investing in the religious trainings for the diaspora. Bruce (2018) analyzed the various religious activities organized by Turkey and Morocco and concluded that these states have recently become more involved in such trainings not merely to serve their diaspora, but as a religious foreign policy to influence the religious discourse

in Europe. The International Theology Programme (UIP) is a significant example of Turkish state-funded religious initiatives designed to meet the needs of the Turkish Muslim community. Bruce (2019) argued that UIP represents a religious diaspora policy that boosts the Turkish transnational governmentality over its diaspora by producing a state-friendly discourse that reinforces state control over the religious field abroad.

Some academics have approached the issue of religious authority from a gender perspective stressing the male dominance in the traditional transmission of religious knowledge. Jouili and Amir-Moazami (2006) highlighted the increasing involvement of women in the religious field, through the various roles they play within their communities, thereby boosting their agency and participation in the making and shaping of the religious authority. A significant contribution in this regard is Bano and Kalmbach’s edited book that highlighted women’s emergence and increasing involvement in the religious field through the analysis of various cases where women

played a leading role in shaping contemporary religious authority and discourses.

Through her analysis of Moroccan gender-based reform, Borrillo’s study (2018) argues that the latter does not represent any real revolution in gender equality, as it may seem; rather, it just reinforces the patriarchal discourse promoting the division of labor. However, given their ability to transcend the public/private space, they can be considered as agents of change.

Although the reviewed studies diverge in their foci and contexts, most of them converge in approaching imams from a more pragmatic and top-down perspective. They tend to look at these religious “authorities” from above (i.e. those in power) by zooming in on how they are perceived by political authorities either in their home or receiving countries. Sometimes, they are seen with excessive suspicion and framed as a political concern that the state must put under scrutiny. Then again, they are perceived as being instrumentalized and framed as a political opportunity that should be seized to facilitate

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the state's policies (namely promoting integration and fighting extremism). In this regard, Peter (2006) affirmed that many studies examined the role of the imam from the majority's angle rather considering the complexity of the role of the imam in the diasporic context. Few studies have approached the issue from a holistic and/or bottom-up perspective by looking at religious authority not only as a process but also from the grassroots' angle. By holistically, I mean the need to investigate the issue of religious authorities more in depth while exploring various actors involved in its making, including Muslim communities, imams, and the political authorities. Sunier's (2018) study is a good example of studies that analyzed the dynamics of construction and incorporation of such formal religious authority into informal contexts of "ordinary" Muslims. While this approach highlights the social construction of Islamic authority, rather framing it as an institutionalized product, it values the individual experiences emphasizing the agency of the "ordinary" Muslims in this process. Another way to investigate the issue of imams is

through an inside-out approach that places the "imam", rather than the political authorities, at the very center of the analysis. In more practical terms, there is a need for studies that examine the various aspects and variables that affect the status and performance of the imam within the diaspora including the requirements, expectations, challenges et cetera. This would help to mirror the actual, rather than their potential impact and address the "conflicting" attitudes towards imams and hopefully provide better suggestions for meeting the expectations of the target diasporic communities (Van Bruinessen, 2013).

In short, as the Muslim population is growing and becoming an integral part of Europe, policy makers can no longer turn a blind eye on the religious needs of the Muslim communities. Moreover, given the dynamic nature of religious authority, further research in this regard is still needed especially in today's precarious digital world.

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Religious Authority and Knowledge Transmission in the Sufi Tradition

By Justin Mauro Benavidez (ESR 12)

In the 14th century Islamic Mediterranean, Muslim intellectuals were engaged in a debate over the issue of authority and legitimacy. Ibn 'Abbad of Ronda (d. 792/1390), the imām and Friday preacher of the Qarawiyyīn Mosque—the intellectual center of North Africa in that period—was at the center of the debate. He argued that it was essential for a disciple on the path of Sufism to take an oath of allegiance with a Sufi-shaykh and submit himself wholly to him. This requirement had a significant impact on the way knowledge was to be received and transmitted: knowledge was passed from master to student but what also passed was an inexplicable esoteric experience.

This Sufi principle alarmed some jurists such that the debate came to involve leading jurists from Cairo and Tunis to Fez and Granada. Some Sufis claimed authority over the Muslim community, a role that had been traditionally held by the guardians of normative Islam, the jurists (fuqahā'). This issue has been well studied in modern historiography. However, what has not been

examined more closely is Ibn 'Abbād's thought on the concept of certainty (yaqīn). His concept of yaqīn is articulated in several of his works on Sufism. One of his principle works is The Major Letters, which is a collection of letters of correspondence between him and his disciple and intimate friend, Yahyā.

Who speaks for Islam and Muslims? Who is vested with the authority to guide the community (umma)? Who explains to the umma God's law on earth or how to obtain proximity (metaphysical) to God? To what extent do scholars exert authority, and how can that authority be assessed? What is the role of Islam's intellectual institutions, such as the mosque, university, or even orders such as tariqas? Religious authority in Islam—as it is in other religious traditions—is an elusive concept and notoriously difficult to define. From a very early period, Muslim intellectuals came to treat questions of authority and legitimacy along epistemological lines, and they approached every matter of the revealed law through their methodologies and terminologies. While religious authority is an important theme,

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more important are the religious authorities themselves, who project and exert authority within a certain context. Jurists and Sufis, for example, have long been concerned with questions of authority and legitimacy. Moreover, jurists and Sufis have discussed, debated, and clashed over who the rightful guardians of Islam are.

Sherman Jackson (2002) writes that throughout Islamic history theology and Sufism were disciplines with which an adherent of a “unorthodox” position could be either included within the fold of Islam or excluded. The disciplines served to show who was “in” and who was “out.” On the controversies concerning orthodoxy and orthopraxy in the 14th century Islamic Mediterranean, Alexander D. Knysh (1999) gives thorough account of the tradition of discussion of Ibn ‘Arabī in both the juridical and theological literature and includes a chapter on the discussion by intellectuals of the Muslim West (al-Andalus and the medieval Maghrib). The controversy that surrounded Ibn ‘Arabī in the West was the familiar conflict between the jurist (the traditional guardian of normative Islam) and Sufis over

formal public religion and private spiritual experience. The concern was that if someone can come close to God through mystical experience, then following the rules of the law might no longer be necessary. Perhaps one point that can be taken up against Knysh is his argument that Andalusī and Maghribī jurists refrained from classifying a thinker like Ibn ‘Arabī a disbeliever (kāfir). While some jurists debated his heterodoxy, theologians did not hesitate to label a heretic a kāfir.

These two religious authorities share a long and complex history, a relationship that is quite misunderstood. Indeed, one of the prevalent misnomers in Islamic Studies has been that of the perennial conflict between the jurist and Sufi, legalist and mystic, doctor and saint, or sharī‘a and haqīqa. In this vein, recent scholarship has produced historical surveys of the criticism of and opposition to mystical conceptions of Islam and their authorities. Frederick de Jong’s and Bernd Radtke’s edited volume (1999) is comprised of contributions that show the problematic nature of the rigid and false dichotomy between Sufism

and normative Islam. Of particular importance, and relevance, are articles by Maribel Fierro (1999) and Vincent Cornell (1999). Fierro provides a brief survey of Sufism in al-Andalus and discusses the problem of religious authority and particular contested practices between the jurist and Sufi in 14th century Nasrid Granada. Cornell’s article is based on his monography (1998), which is a culmination of twenty years of research on sainthood and Sufism in al-Andalus and the Maghrib from the 11th through the 16th centuries. The networks of transmission of Islamic knowledge and the mobility patterns of scholars of pre-modern Morocco have also received critical study. The international links between the learned of the central lands of Islam and the Maghrib are an important factor in the role played by Sufis in the development of Islamic law. Cornell shows that Maghribī Sufis learned and spread exoteric knowledge. As such, in bringing back the Shāfi‘ī or usūlī legal methodology to the Islamic West, Sufis became active agents of Sunni internationalism against local sectarian views of the Shī‘ī and Khārijī; and also against the early Mālikī’s reliance on local practice (‘amal).

With respect to the broader Islamic intellectual history, a number of important works have increased our understanding of the role of educational institutions and networks played in the transmission of knowledge between teachers and students. The beginning point for any study of medieval Islamic institutions and education is George Makdisi’s path-breaking *The Rise of Colleges* (1981). As the title suggests, the book studies the origins and development of Islam’s educational institution, the madrasa, or college. Despite the book’s faults and the fact that it attempted to cover a vast intellectual region and period, the work prompted scholars to follow up on Makdisi’s work. Jonathan Berkey’s (1992) *The Transmission of Knowledge in Medieval Cairo*, among many other facets of knowledge, shows more clearly than any historian before him that it was personal, rather than institutional, relationships that constituted the core of Islamic education. Michael Chamberlain (2002) examines the role of the madrasa in Damascene society in a different light and contends that the institution of the madrasa has been poorly understood.

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